

IMPACT OF ENERGY CONSUMPTION ON NIGERIA'S AGRICULTURAL ECONOMIC GROWTH (1988-2018)

Victor Ukoha

Independent Researcher

Lagos, Nigeria

victor.ukoha@usercando.com

The relationship between energy consumption, carbon emissions, and economic growth is critical for understanding the sustainability of agricultural practices in developing economies. This study examines Nigeria's agricultural sector, focusing on key subsectors: crop production, forestry, fishing, and livestock. Using data from 1988 to 2018 sourced from the Nigeria Bureau of Statistics, this paper analyzes energy consumption patterns, emissions, and their economic impacts were analyzed through the Logarithmic Mean Divisia Index (LMDI). The findings reveal that energy efficiency in the agricultural sector fluctuated between 20.47% and 22.46%, driven by fuel-specific contributions from premium motor spirit, automotive gas oil, and fuel oil. Decomposition analysis identifies activity effects as the predominant driver of emissions, with crop production contributing the largest share, followed by forestry and fishing. Probabilistic modelling further highlights sectoral disparities: while emissions from forestry and fishing negatively affect GDP by 0.01779 and 0.05504 units per emission unit, respectively, emissions from crop production show a positive correlation, contributing an increase of 0.031 units per emission unit. The findings offer a roadmap for optimizing energy use, reducing

emissions, and promoting sustainable agriculture in Nigeria and similar economies globally.

Keywords: Energy-Efficiency Optimization, Economic-Environmental Nexus, Carbon Emission Reduction Strategies.

1.1 ENERGY CONSUMPTION PATTERN IN NIGERIA

Energy consumption patterns in the world today shows that Nigeria and indeed African countries have the lowest rates of consumption. Nevertheless, Nigeria suffers from an inadequate supply of usable energy due to the rapidly increasing demand, which is typical of a developing economy. Unexpectedly, the country is potentially endowed with sustainable energy resources. Nigeria is rich in conventional energy resources, which include oil, natural gas, lignite, and coal. It is also well endowed with renewable energy sources such as wood, solar, hydropower, and wind (Okafor *et al.*, 2010). The patterns of energy usage in Nigeria's economy can be divided into industrial, transport, commercial, agricultural, and household sectors (ECN, 2003). The household sector accounts for the largest share of energy usage in the country - about 65%. This is largely due to the low level of development in all the other sectors.

The major energy-consuming activities in Nigeria's households are cooking, lighting, and use of electrical appliances. Cooking accounts for a staggering 91% of household energy consumption, lighting uses up to 6%, and the remaining 3% can be attributed to the use of basic electrical appliances such as televisions and pressing irons (ECN, 2005). The predominant energy resources for domestic and commercial uses in Nigeria are fuel wood, charcoal, kerosene, cooking gas and electricity (Famuyide *et al.*, 2011). Other sources, though less common, are sawdust, agricultural crop residues of corn stalk, cassava sticks, and, in extreme cases, cow dung. In Nigeria, among the urban dwellers, kerosene and gas are the major cooking fuels. The majority of the people rely

on kerosene stoves for domestic cooking, while only a few use gas and electric cookers (Abiodun, 2003). The rural areas have little access to conventional energy such as electricity and petroleum products due to the absence of good road networks. Petroleum products such as kerosene and gasoline are purchased in the rural areas at prices very high in excess of their official pump prices. The rural population, whose needs are often basic, therefore depends to a large extent on fuel wood as a major traditional source of fuel. It has been estimated that about 86 % of rural households in Nigeria depend on fuel wood as their source of energy (Williams, 1998). A fuel wood supply/demand imbalance in some parts of the country is now a real threat to the energy security of the rural communities (ECN, 2003).

The energy consumption per capita in Nigeria is very small - about one-sixth of the energy consumed in developed countries. This is directly linked to the level of poverty in the country. Gross domestic product (GDP) and per capita income are indices that are used to measure the economic well-being of a country and its people (Karekezi, 1997). GDP is defined as the total market value of all final goods and services produced within a given country in a given period of time, usually a calendar year. The per capita income refers to how much each individual receives, in monetary terms, of the yearly income that is generated in a country through productive activities. That is what each citizen would receive if the yearly income generated by a country from its productive activities were divided equally between everyone.

In the past three decades, Nigeria has witnessed an increase in energy consumption. From 1980 to 2008 the energy consumption has increased steadily at an annual rate of 9.2%, followed by a decrease of 5.4% in 2010 and then an increase of 20.5% in 2011 (NNBS, 2012). Nigeria's expectation is to be among the 20 industrialized nations of the world. By this projection, it is expected that the energy consumption will surely increase in all the sectors due to expected increase in economic activities. The energy production and consumption sectors are faced with numerous challenges including low energy generation, low energy efficiency, high losses in conversion processes, poor management systems and high environmental degradation and emissions (Obadote, 2009). For Nigeria to make meaningful progress in her energy crusade, the country will need to address the issues of low energy efficiency, ensure energy optimization in all sectors of the economy, improve environmental and social security and initiate a proper energy management system to meet the requirements for sustainable development.

1.2 Empirical Studies on Emissions and Economic Growth

Some empirical studies have been carried out to assess the impact of carbon emissions and pollution on growth. Porter and Brown (2009) found out in their study that emissions from fossil fuels have a negative and significant impact on economic growth. They claimed that the negative impact is as a result of low productivity of both land and labour caused by increased carbon emissions. Though in a different study, Baltimore and Tudok (2010) found out that there is a positive relationship between carbon emissions

and growth. He said this is due to the fact that emissions result from industrial activities, which enhance growth. Stern (2009) considers the causal relationship between different types of energy consumption and GDP in Taiwan for the period 1980–2005, which was his second major analysis. Using different types of energy consumption he found a bi-directional causality between energy and GDP. This result contradicts with Cheng (2006) who found that there is a unidirectional causal relationship from GDP to energy use in Taiwan.

Torras and Boyce (2008) gave some causes of carbon emission. They said that economic growth leads to the emission of more carbon. This is because growth results from industrialization, which promotes the consumption of fossil fuels and natural gases. According to Sanglimsuwan (2011), population can be a driving force behind the increase in emissions. Population density is defined by mid-year population divided by land area in square kilometers. The definition of population is all residents regardless of legal status or citizenship. Land area is a country's total area, excluding area under inland water bodies. Sanglimsuwan (2011) showed that government effectiveness can positively influence environmental quality through higher performance on good policies, and effective implementation of policies. Government effectiveness index, according to Torras and Boyce (2008), is a measure of the quality of public service provision, the quality of the bureaucracy, the competence of civil servants, the independence of the civil service from political pressures, and the credibility of the government's commitment to policies. Mesih and Mesih (2009) found in their study that carbon emissions from gas flaring or gas fuels and solid fuels have significant impact on economic growth. A unit

rise in the emissions of these fuels leads to 0.34 and 0.52 units increases in GDP, respectively. Thus, they found out that emissions have a positive impact on economic growth. They added that the major sources of carbon emission in Asia are gas fuels and solid fuels.

Studies show that biological productivity in Nigeria will decrease in the event of global warming (Adesina and Adejuwom, 2008) with an additional consequence of severe fuelwood shortages. Already Nigeria has experienced a definite shift in the long-term rainfall mean towards more arid conditions. These climatic changes have had adverse implications for water resources availability for power generation and agriculture. The above analysis clearly suggests that it will not only be economically beneficial for Nigeria to craft a climate change-response development strategy, but that factoring climate change abatement into the overall economic development plan is also crucial for its own self-preservation. This will help to reduce the adverse effects of carbon emissions on economic growth.

1.3 Studies Relating Energy Consumption and Economic Growth

Economic growth is characterised by energy demand. Therefore, it is true that consumption is derived from demand. Accordingly, Birol (2007) maintained that demand for energy has surged resulting in the unrelenting increase which has helped to trigger global economic growth. Asafu-Adjaye (2000) performed a similar research on Singapore and Indonesia respectively and found out the same unidirectional causality effect of

energy consumption and economic growth. The positive relationship between electricity and economic growth has been justified by some authors as being consistent. Many economists agree that there is a strong correlation between energy usage and economic development. In that regard, Morimoto & Hope (2001) have discovered, using Pearson correlation coefficient, that economic growth and energy consumption in Sri Lanka are highly correlated. Similar studies that relate economic growth and energy consumption nexus are reviewed as follows. Aqeel & Butt, (2001) performed a co-integration test on energy and its relationship with economic growth in Pakistan, with results showing that increase in electricity consumption leads to economic growth. Soytas and Sari, (2003) performed a test on the causality between energy consumption and GDP in the top ten emerging markets excluding China and G-7 countries. The results found out bidirectional causality in Argentina, unidirectional causality running from energy consumption to GDP in Turkey, France, Germany and Japan, and from GDP to energy consumption in Korea and Italy. Soytas *et al.* carried out an examination of the relationship between energy consumption and GDP for Turkey between 1960 and 1995 with results which found a unidirectional relationship from energy consumption to GDP for the period.

Furthermore, Costantini & Martini (2009) analysed the causal relationship between the economy and energy by adopting a Vector Error Correction Model for non-stationary and cointegrated panel data with a large sample of developed and developing countries and four distinct energy sectors. The results showed that alternative country samples hardly affect the causality relations, particularly in a multivariate multi-sector framework. Apart from a number of studies which considered energy as a whole,

others have examined energy by separating it into its sub-component such as electricity and petroleum. Accordingly, Jumbe (2004) examined the relationship between electricity consumption and GDP for Malawi for the period between 1970 and 1999 and found a bidirectional causal relationship. He also examined the relationship between non-agricultural GDP and electricity consumption where he found a unidirectional causality relationship from GDP to energy consumption. Rufael, (2006) investigated the relationship between electricity consumption and GDP for 17 Africa countries from 1971 through 2001 periods. The result showed the existence of cointegrating relationships in 9 countries and Granger causality for 12 countries. Unidirectional causality from GDP to electricity consumption was found in 6 of these countries and from electricity consumption to GDP in 3 of them. Also, Bidirectional was found in 3 countries. Zou and Chau, (2005) examined the relationship between oil consumption and GDP in the pre-liberalization (1953-1984) and post-liberalization (1985-2002) Chinese economy. The study found co-integration between oil consumption and GDP for 1953-1984 periods, it found no causality between the variables in the short run, however, they found bidirectional causality in the long run. The study, however, found no cointegration between oil consumption and GDP for the entire period of 1953-2002.

Erbaykal, (2008) investigated the relationship between economic growth and energy disaggregation using oil and electricity consumption for 1970-2003 periods in Turkey with Bounds test approach to cointegration. The results showed that, in the short run, both oil and electricity consumption have positive significant effects on economic growth. (Ang, 1995) studied the decomposition of industrial energy consumption in

Singapore at two levels of sector disaggregation. Ang and Lee, (1996) examined the impact of structural change and changes in sectoral energy efficiencies for Singapore by decomposing the industrial energy consumption. Sun, (2001) used a decomposition model for predicting aggregate energy demand in 15 European Union countries. The model was decomposed into components to study the effect of sectoral energy intensity, structure change and GDP. Sari and Soytas, (2004) determined the energy consumption and economic growth relationship by examining how much of the variance in national income growth can be explained by the growth of different sources of energy consumption and employment in Turkey. A generalized forecast error variance decomposition technique was used to determine the information content of the growth rate of energy consumption in Turkey. Lee and Chien, (2010) applied an aggregate production function to examine the relationship among energy consumption, capital stock, and real income (real GDP per capita) in G-7 countries. Granger causality test, the generalized impulse response approach, and variance decompositions in a multivariate setting was used to determine the extent and magnitude of the relationship among variables. Decomposition models are also applied source-wise, for oil and electricity. The studies carried out for oil and electricity based on the decomposition model are also reviewed. Tao, (2010) used Factor Decomposition method and System Dynamics (SD) modelling to predict the pattern of future oil consumption per capita. Three factors were used for decomposition, i.e. economic activity, technological progress, and structure of energy consumption. Afshar and Bigdeli, (2011) performed a short term load forecasting for Iran electricity market using singular spectral analysis (SSA). SSA decomposes a time

series into trend and oscillation components. The simulation results showed that the method gave better results.

Unit root test and cointegration models have also been employed in the analysis and projection of energy management systems. Hondroyannis *et al.* (2002) used the vector error-correction model estimation to examine the relationship between energy consumption and economic growth for Greece. The vector specification includes energy consumption, real GDP and price developments – the latter taken to represent a measure of economic efficiency. The results indicated that there is a long-run relationship between the three variables, supporting the endogeneity of energy consumption and real output. Galindo, (2005) presented the demand for the different types of energy consumption for Mexico. The Johansen procedure and the likelihood ratio tests were used to find the relationship between the types of energy and income. It was found that in Mexico the demand for energy is driven by income and relative prices. Lee and Chang, (2005) examined the stability between energy consumption and GDP for Taiwan. Aggregate and disaggregate data of energy consumption, including coal, oil, gas, and electricity, was used. Unit root tests and the cointegration tests allowing for structural breaks were performed on the data. Following similar lines, Lee and Chien, (2010) used the panel unit root testing procedure with multiple structural breaks to re-investigate the stationarity of energy consumption per capita across regions of the world. Elsewhere, the co-integration between energy consumption and GDP were analysed for Turkey by Lise and Montfort, (2007). The short term variation was predicted using a vector error correction model

(ECM). The causality between variables was determined using the Granger causality model.

1.4 State of Energy Consumption Modelling in the Agricultural Sector in Nigeria

Although the agricultural sector is among the predominant energy sectors in the country, very little is devoted in literature on studies relating its energy efficiency. The studies on energy efficiency and status of selected sectors have recently been reported in the residential and transport sectors. For instance, Badmus *et al.* (2014) examined the end-use efficiencies of the different energy carriers and the overall energy efficiency in the Nigerian residential sector (NRS) using energy and exergy analysis. The energy and exergy flows were considered from 2006 to 2011. The overall energy efficiency ranges from 19.15 % in 2006 to 20.19 % in 2011 while the overall energy efficiency ranges from 4.34 % in 2006 to 4.40 % in 2011. The energy and exergy efficiency margin was 15.58 % with a marginal improvement of 0.07 % and 0.02 %, respectively when compared with previous results. The contribution of the energy carriers to the total energy and exergy inputs were 1.45 % and 1.43 % for electricity, 1.95 % and 3 % for fossil fuel and 96.6 % and 95.57 % for biofuel. The result shows that approximately 65 % of the residents use wood and biomass for domestic cooking and heating, and only a fraction of the residents have access to electricity.

In a related study, Badmus *et al.* analysed the energy utilisation in the transportation sector of Nigeria using exergy methods. The sector is dominated by the road subsector, with a share ranging from 70.65% in 1990 to 97.51% in the year 2005 and a mean of 88.44%. The road subsector is still the most efficient, with energy efficiency values that range from 9.93% in 1990 to 19.19% in 1986. The corresponding exergy values are 9.28% and 17.93%, respectively. Following the road subsector is the aviation subsector with its least energy consumption share of 0.10% in 2005 and biggest share of 26.25% in 1990. The sub sector energy efficiency values range from 0.03% in 2005 to 7.35% in 1990, with corresponding exergy values of 0.026 % and 6.87 %, respectively. The overall mean energy efficiency in the Nigerian transportation sector for the three decades was 17.11 %, while the overall mean energy efficiency was 15.97 %. The road sub sector performance has been adversely affected by the massive importation of used vehicles into the country.

A similar study by Badmus and Osunleke (2010) reports a sectoral energy study approach for the residential sector in Nigeria for a period of 15 years from 1991 to 2005. The energy and exergy flows considered included the commercial and the 'non-commercial' energy sources. The most efficiently utilised energy source appears to be the Liquefied Petroleum Gas and the least efficient, kerosene. Electricity utilisation exergy efficiency has been adversely affected by the vapour-compression air-conditioning application apart from low potential thermal energy applications. The overall utilisation energy and exergy efficiencies were found to be 19.89 % and 4.38 %, respectively.

A summary of the literature shows no detailed study on energy studies and efficiency in the agricultural sector of Nigeria. Such an energy study will aid in framing the right energy mix structure to encourage productivity in the agricultural sector. Since the objective of the study is to address the quantitative relationship between energy consumption, corresponding emissions and economic growth, its results will aid in creating one of several energy management blueprints necessary for a greener environment.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Globally, efforts to match increasing energy demand from the teeming population has resulted in serious environmental hazards. These environmental concerns have resulted in the changes in atmospheric imbalance in recent years. Such hazards include, among others, the vulnerability of the economic sector to the recurrent droughts, flood and cyclones, decline of some plant and animal populations, spread of diseases vectors including malaria, freezing and breaking-up of ice on rivers and lakes, reduction in food production, increase in death rate and threat to sustainable development. Interestingly, one of the cost effective measures in reducing emissions impact is to identify the extent to which each energy carrier has both the emission mantra and economic growth in all sectors of the economy. In the light of this development, the current study seeks to highlight the particular effect of the consumption of several energy carriers on both economic growth and environmental degradation. The results will help guide policy makers and investors in making wise energy investment decisions in the near future.

2.1 Aim of the Study

The aim of the study is the analysis of the impact of energy consumption and economic growth in the Nigerian agricultural sector.

The objectives of the study is highlighted below:

1. To identify and assess the energy consumption mix utilized in the agricultural sector.
2. To quantify greenhouse gas emission resulting from the current energy use structure in the sector.
3. To perform a probabilistic analysis of the relationship between emissions, economic growth, and energy consumption in the agricultural sector.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Energy Consumption Decomposition Modelling

The magnitude of economic growth and emissions on energy consumption is a function of several indices which is often related in economic models to check the nexus between these variables. Several models have been proposed and implemented in this regard to check to what extent an energy indicator affects the overall growth pattern as a weighted coefficient and probability (Apergis *et al.*, 2011; Bhattacharya *et al.*, 2016; Bowden & Payne, 2009; Canay, 2011), or as a combination of decomposed constituents (Ang, 2004). In this study, these two methods are considered in assessing the extent to which energy consumption and economic growth are related in the agricultural sector in Nigeria. The next section considers the general first principles method in modelling energy consumption as a combination of decomposed constituents using three indicators.

3.1.1 Energy Consumption from Decomposed Indicators

The method for analysing the consumption trend is an identity approach which in its elementary form considers the degree of relative contributions of key drivers. With properly weighted combination of factors, the method is developed to reflect the extent economic activity α , energy matrix β , and energy intensity γ affect energy consumption. These variables are properly accounted for in the methodology which is developed as follows (Sun, 2003): The energy consumption is represented as:

$$\psi = f|\alpha\beta\gamma| \quad 3.1$$

Equ. 3.1 is rewritten as Equ. 3.2 since its terms are related to other factors in fractional form:

$$\psi = \alpha * \beta * \gamma \quad 3.2$$

Terms of Equ. 3.2 are represented as:

$$\psi = f|E| = f|\alpha, \beta, \gamma| \quad 3.3$$

$$\alpha = f|E, GDP| \quad 3.4$$

$$\beta = f|GDP, GDP_i| \quad 3.5$$

$$\gamma = f|GDP| \quad 3.6$$

The energy consumption at a reference time t_0 and later time T can also be represented

as:

$$\psi^{t_0} = \alpha^{t_0} \beta^{t_0} \gamma^{t_0} \quad 3.7$$

$$\psi^T = \alpha^T \beta^T \gamma^T \quad 3.8$$

The change in the value of ψ can then be written as:

$$\Delta\psi = \psi^T - \psi^{t_0} = \alpha^T \beta^T \gamma^T - \alpha^{t_0} \beta^{t_0} \gamma^{t_0} \quad 3.9$$

According to Sun, (2001) the changes in Equation 3.9 can be written as:

$$\Delta\psi = \Delta\psi_{\alpha} + \Delta\psi_{\beta} + \Delta\psi_{\gamma}$$

3.10

$$\Delta\psi_{\alpha} = \Delta\alpha * \beta^{t_0} * \gamma^{t_0} + \frac{1}{2}\Delta\alpha * \Delta\beta * \gamma^{t_0} + \frac{1}{2}\Delta\alpha * \beta^{t_0} * \Delta\gamma + \frac{1}{3}\Delta\alpha * \Delta\beta * \Delta\gamma \quad 3.11$$

$$\Delta\psi_{\beta} = \alpha^{t_0} * \Delta\beta * \gamma^{t_0} + \frac{1}{2}\Delta\alpha * \Delta\beta * \gamma^{t_0} + \frac{1}{2}\alpha^{t_0} * \Delta\beta * \Delta\gamma + \frac{1}{3}\Delta\alpha * \Delta\beta * \Delta\gamma \quad 3.12$$

$$\Delta\psi_{\gamma} = \alpha^{t_0} * \beta^{t_0} * \Delta\gamma + \frac{1}{2}\Delta\alpha * \beta^{t_0} * \Delta\gamma + \frac{1}{2}\alpha^{t_0} * \Delta\beta * \Delta\gamma + \frac{1}{3}\Delta\alpha * \Delta\beta * \Delta\gamma \quad 3.13$$

3.2 Carbon Dioxide Emissions from Multiple Decomposed Indicators

The analysis described in section 3.1.1 allows the consideration of the emissions as a function of three drivers. However, several other factors affect the emissions trend which must be captured in an integrated approach. Such a method is adopted using the following approach. The empirical model required to calculate the quantity of carbon dioxide emissions from fossil energy is presented by quantifying the contributions of five different factors: scale of the economy, industrial activity mix, sectoral energy intensity, sectoral energy mix, and the values of emission factors. Additionally, different sub-categories are considered, concerning industrial sectors and fuel type. The carbon dioxide emissions can be written as (Robalino *et al.*, 2013; 2014):

$$C = \sum_{ij} C_{ij} = Q \sum_{ij} \frac{Q_i}{Q} \frac{E_i}{E_i} \frac{E_{ij}}{E_{ij}} \frac{C_{ij}}{E_{ij}} = Q \sum_{ij} S_i * I_i * M_{ij} * U_{ij} \quad 3.14$$

The terms of equation 3.14 are labelled as follows:

C is the total carbon dioxide emissions for the whole sectors in a given year;

C_{ij} is the total carbon dioxide emissions arising from fuel type j in the i^{th} sector;

Q is the total GDP of the country;

Q_i is the GDP generated by the i^{th} sector;

E_i is the energy consumption in the i^{th} sector;

E_{ij} is the energy due to consumption of fuel j in the i^{th} sector;

S_i is the share of the GDP of the i^{th} sector to the total GDP of the considered sectors;

I_i is the energy intensity in the i^{th} sector;

M_{ij} is the energy matrix expressed for the i^{th} sector as the energy from fuel type j to the total energy in the sector;

U_{ij} is the carbon dioxide emission factor for the i^{th} sector.

Although very detailed data as outlined in the expressions above for particular sectors and the fuel types are not readily available for Nigeria, however, a sum of the nation's economic growth and accompanying carbon dioxide emissions can be found in the Nigeria Bureau of Statistics Bulletin as well as the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin annually. From Equation 3.14, the following can be obtained (Ang, 2004, 2005; Ang *et al.*, (2002, 2003).

$$\sum_{ij} C_{ij} = \Delta C_{act} + \Delta C_{str} + \Delta C_{int} + \Delta C_{mix} + \Delta C_{emf} \quad 3.15$$

The terms in equation 3.15 are expressed as:

$$\Delta C_{act} = \sum_i \left(\frac{C_{ij}^T - C_{ij}^0}{\ln[C_{ij}^T] - \ln[C_{ij}^0]} \right) \ln \left[\frac{Q^T}{Q^0} \right] \quad 3.16$$

$$\Delta C_{str} = \sum_i \left(\frac{C_{ij}^T - C_{ij}^0}{\ln[C_{ij}^T] - \ln[C_{ij}^0]} \right) \ln \left[\frac{S_i^T}{S_i^0} \right] \quad 3.17$$

$$\Delta C_{int} = \sum_i \left(\frac{C_{ij}^T - C_{ij}^0}{\ln[C_{ij}^T] - \ln[C_{ij}^0]} \right) \ln \left[\frac{I_i^T}{I_i^0} \right] \quad 3.18$$

$$\Delta C_{mix} = \sum_i \left(\frac{C_{ij}^T - C_{ij}^0}{\ln[C_{ij}^T] - \ln[C_{ij}^0]} \right) \ln \left[\frac{M_{ij}^T}{M_{ij}^0} \right] \quad 3.19$$

$$\Delta C_{emf} = \sum_i \left(\frac{C_{ij}^T - C_{ij}^0}{\ln[C_{ij}^T] - \ln[C_{ij}^0]} \right) \ln \left[\frac{U_{ij}^T}{U_{ij}^0} \right] \quad 3.20$$

3.3 Carbon Dioxide Emissions on GDP from Weighted Coefficient and Probability

The method of weighted coefficient and probability employs a linearized relationship between the emissions trend and several emission indicators linked to the **GDP**. The model considers the relative contributions from combustion processes in crop production (CP), forestry (FST), fishing (FSH) and livestock (LVS) on gross domestic products GDP.

The following expression can be used for cointegrating the emission carriers as follows:

$$GDP = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 CP_T + \alpha_2 FST_T + \alpha_3 FSH_T + \alpha_4 LVS_T \quad 3.21$$

To allow for enhanced correlation between the GDP and its driving factors, a residual term is added which must be optimised. The solution is provided using Microsoft Excel. The coefficients of Equation 3.21 are determined using the data in the next section.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Summary of Energy Consumption in the Agricultural Sector

To aid in the analysis of the relation between energy structure, consumption pattern, and the emissions mantra, energy data has been collected and is hereby presented. The data was obtained from the archives of the Nigeria Bureau of Statistics (NBS) for the years 1988 through 2018. The data covers areas like the country's gross domestic product (GDP), the energy consumption in different agricultural subsectors, and the corresponding emissions from these energy use. The structured data contains energy consumption in crop production (PMS and AGO), forestry (PMS), fishing (PMS and AGO) and livestock (AGO). The data also contains the respective gross domestic product in the mentioned fields. The data summary is shown in Tables 4.1 and 4.2.

Table 4.1: Annual Energy Consumption and GDP for Crop Production and Forestry in the Agricultural Sector.

Year	Crop production			Forestry	
	Energy (PJ)		GDP (N Million)	Energy(PJ)	GDP (N Million)
	PMS	AGO		AGO	
1988	121.7725	33.43869	N/A	29.09347	N/A
1989	152.9379	39.31714	2326.70	36.53939	124.30
1990	171.9794	41.96783	1905.10	41.08871	163.00
1991	177.8283	43.31493	1860.90	42.48611	161.30
1992	169.3456	40.37992	2089.80	40.45947	169.20
1993	169.1236	37.06686	3030.50	40.40643	198.00
1994	154.016	31.8384	3171.10	17.81905	183.50
1995	155.5185	29.60361	3430.02	19.4459	198.98
1996	165.428	32.69032	3709.98	14.26591	210.92

1997	187.5791	34.40722	4019.58	14.86699	212.52
1998	185.69	40.98399	4665.62	84.22042	248.53
1999	185.7925	41.00136	5293.84	16.03079	252.26
2000	187.1253	32.13304	8050.81	19.40576	346.26
2001	226.9443	57.92496	13548.18	17.59855	506.60
2002	239.8583	39.73802	29826.64	15.43368	683.94
2003	175.6138	38.98208	46687.45	16.21381	833.07
2004	169.48	38.95989	60621.68	15.32255	943.88
2005	168.4867	45.59488	69676.07	18.51314	1143.95
2006	150.1318	31.13056	90067.63	1.154097	1225.18
2007	134.116	27.371	106212.07	1.430163	1381.40
2008	190.2686	38.30822	116337.70	0.434826	1651.97
2009	250.76	46.13529	129967.75	59.91069	1889.79
2010	275.4001	41.35251	160679.90	12.09123	2519.23
2011	271.5041	39.35402	205936.69	14.31883	2759.18
2012	258.2866	24.72426	344913.02	3.17961	3009.64
2013	307.2292	34.92473	362605.26	0.345229	3282.82
2014	376.2422	23.36103	416240.26	10.71834	4023.88
2015	328.5612	10.77207	444989.96	12.11762	4567.79
2016	306.4878	21.89909	450329.84	37.05917	4622.60
2017	292.4471	11.15277	475907.25	28.11002	5243.09
2018	386.5995	22.98541	495756.16	7.251688	5866.03

Source: Nigerian Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2019)

Table 4.2. Annual Energy Consumption and GDP for Fishing and Livestock in the Agricultural Sector

Year	Fishing			Livestock	
	Energy (PJ)		GDP (N Million)	Energy (PJ)	GDP (N Million)
	FO	AGO		AGO	
1988	3.240969	5.015804	N/A	N/A	N/A
1989	4.530618	5.89757	232.90	N/A	110.60
1990	4.77431	6.295174	291.70	N/A	128.30
1991	5.1045	6.49724	330.00	N/A	110.50
1992	3.526152	6.056989	271.40	N/A	109.30
1993	3.225455	5.560029	253.10	N/A	131.50
1994	4.618205	4.775761	265.40	N/A	138.33
1995	5.122074	4.440541	281.69	N/A	93.72
1996	5.371018	4.903548	311.50	N/A	79.80
1997	4.209882	5.161084	276.08	N/A	58.73
1998	3.8117	6.147598	280.80	N/A	59.91
1999	3.8117	6.150204	333.73	N/A	59.29
2000	3.287308	4.819956	312.51	N/A	42.69

2001	3.372632	8.688743	460.35	N/A	58.75
2002	3.277086	5.960703	435.05	N/A	2.85
2003	5.843981	5.847312	502.48	N/A	2.44
2004	7.501553	5.843984	569.34	N/A	2.94
2005	10.00649	6.839232	641.95	2.021	3.66
2006	6.385382	4.669583	671.13	1.333	3.93
2007	3.273578	4.10565	703.01	1.376	4.19
2008	0.959548	5.746234	762.46	1.806	4.50
2009	0.93609	6.920293	835.41	1.892	4.93
2010	1.062656	6.202876	829.33	1.548	5.36
2011	6.722852	5.903103	842.40	1.505	5.92
2012	2.252768	3.708639	909.92	1.204	6.41
2013	2.22513	5.23871	982.88	0.946	6.94
2014	1.032407	3.504154	1061.25	N/A	7.53
2015	0.647006	1.61581	1170.70	N/A	9.55
2016	2.143436	3.284864	1184.75	N/A	9.66
2017	1.630987	1.672915	1248.38	N/A	10.22
2018	0.967965	3.447812	1353.72	N/A	10.78

Source: Nigerian Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2019)

* N/A indicates data not available

4.2 Energy Efficiency in the Agricultural Sector

Energy efficiency for the agricultural sector is presented using the data in Tables 4.1 and 4.2. Thereafter, the index decomposition method, derived using the logarithmic mean divisia index is used to decompose energy consumption with respect to the activity, intensity, and structural effects. First, sample calculation of the energy is presented for the year 2016 as follows:

$$\eta_{Agriculture} = 0.8755 * 22 + 0.0995 * 15 + 0.000983 * 23 + 0.00632 * 15 + 0.014 * 15 + 0.0027 * 15$$

Using the sample calculation, results are similarly presented for the years between 1988 through 2018. Energy efficiency for the years considered is presented in

Table 4.3. Furthermore, the results of energy efficiencies are compared with similar results in other countries.

Table 4.3 Summary of Energy Efficiency in the Agricultural Sector

Year	Energy efficiency%
1988	21.3908
1989	21.4608
1990	21.5313
1991	21.5295
1992	21.5882
1993	21.6925
1994	21.1472
1995	21.2645
1996	21.0337
1997	21.1177
1998	22.4635
1999	20.9693
2000	21.3304
2001	20.7781
2002	21.1776
2003	20.9384
2004	20.8436
2005	20.6473
2006	20.4718
2007	20.5769
2008	20.6312
2009	21.9135
2010	21.1749
2011	21.1498
2012	21.3041
2013	21.1415
2014	21.6843
2015	21.9476
2016	22.0838
2017	22.2014
2018	21.6480

The results of energy efficiency in the agricultural sector have been tabulated and presented in Table 4.3 and Fig. 4.1 using the sample calculation and the data presented in

Tables 4.1 and 4.2. The energy efficiencies were fluctuating between 20.47 and 22.46 %.

The values of energy and exergy efficiencies are largely determined by the contributions of consumption of different fuels with respect to their operating efficiencies. The results of average energy efficiencies over the years for Nigeria is compared with other countries of the world in Fig. 4.2.

Fig. 4.1 Overall energies efficiencies between 1988 and 2018

Fig. 4.2 Comparison of energy efficiencies in the agricultural sector in selected countries

4.3 Emissions Decomposition

The carbon dioxide emissions and corresponding energy output which is reflected in the GDP have been presented using the data in Tables 4.1 and 4.2 for the agricultural sector for the years 1988 to 2018. The considered agricultural sub sectors are crop production, forestry, fishing and livestock. Following the methods for the analysis of emissions decomposition into effects, results are presented accordingly. Sample calculation for the year 2012 is made in the light of the LMDI model. The LMDI analysis is a special form of index decomposition analysis which incorporates energy changes in logarithmic mean fashion, accounting for changes regardless of emissions flow direction. A structured data which accounts for the intensity of energy consumption is presented. The considered fuels relevant to the study are premium motor spirit (petrol), automotive gas oil (diesel), and fuel oil. The emission factors for the fuels are enlisted in Table 4.4:

Table 4.4: Fuel related emission factors

Fuel	FO	AGO	PMS
Emissions (tCO ₂ /GJ)	73.6	69.9	67.4
Emissions (tCO ₂ /PJ)	73600000	6990000	67400000

Source: OEE (2003)

Using the emission factors tabulated in Table 4.4, with reference to Equ. 3.39, Tables 4.5 and 4.6 are computed for the various fuels.

Table 4.5 Carbon Dioxide Emissions for Crop Production and Forestry Agriculture**Modes**

Year	Crop production				Forestry	
	PMS (PJ)	Emissions tCO ₂	AGO (PJ)	Emissions tCO ₂	AGO (PJ)	Emissions tCO ₂
1988	121.77	8207466.5	33.44	233736.44	29.09	2024905.512
1989	152.93	10308014.46	39.32	274826.80	36.53	2543141.544
1990	171.97	11591411.56	41.98	293355.13	41.08	2859774.216
1991	177.82	11985627.42	43.32	302771.36	42.48	2957033.256
1992	169.34	11413893.44	40.38	282255.64	40.45	2815979.112
1993	169.12	11398930.64	37.07	259097.35	40.40	2812287.528
1994	154.02	10380678.4	31.84	222550.41	17.82	1240205.88
1995	155.52	10481946.9	29.60	206929.23	19.44	1353434.64
1996	165.43	11149847.2	32.69	228505.33	14.26	992907.336
1997	187.58	12642831.34	34.41	240506.46	14.86	1034742.504
1998	185.69	12515506	40.98	286478.09	84.22	5861741.232
1999	185.79	12522414.5	41.01	286599.50	16.03	1115742.984
2000	187.13	12612245.22	32.13	224609.94	19.40	1350640.896
2001	226.94	15296045.82	57.92	404895.47	17.59	1224859.08
2002	239.85	16166449.42	39.73	277768.75	15.43	1074184.128
2003	175.61	11836370.12	38.98	272484.73	16.21	1128481.176
2004	169.48	11422952	38.95	272329.63	15.32	1066449.48
2005	168.48	11356003.58	45.59	318708.21	18.513	1288514.544
2006	150.13	10118883.32	31.13	217602.61	1.1540	80325.1512
2007	134.12	9039418.4	27.371	191323.29	1.4301	99539.3448
2008	190.26	12824103.64	38.30	267774.45	0.4348	30263.8896
2009	250.76	16901224	46.13	322485.67	59.910	4169784.024
2010	275.40	18561966.74	41.352	289054.04	12.091	841549.608
2011	271.50	18299376.34	39.35	275084.59	14.318	996590.568
2012	258.28	17408516.84	24.72	172822.57	3.1796	221300.856
2013	307.22	20707248.08	34.92	244123.86	0.3452	24027.9384
2014	376.24	25358724.28	23.36	163293.59	10.718	745996.464
2015	328.56	22145024.88	10.77	75296.76	12.117	843386.352
2016	306.48	20657277.72	21.89	153074.63	37.059	2579318.232
2017	292.44	19710934.54	11.15	77957.86	28.110	1956457.392
2018	386.59	26056806.3	22.985	160668.01	7.2516	504717.4848

Table 4.6 Carbon Dioxide Emissions for Fishing and Livestock Agriculture Modes

Year	Fishing				Livestock	
	FO (PJ)	Emission tCO ₂ /PJ	AGO (PJ)	Emission tCO ₂ /PJ	AGO (PJ)	Emission tCO ₂ /PJ
1988	3.240969	238535.3	5.015804	35060.47	N/A	N/A
1989	4.530618	333453.5	5.89757	41224.01	N/A	N/A
1990	4.77431	351389.2	6.295174	44003.27	N/A	N/A
1991	5.1045	375691.2	6.49724	45415.71	N/A	N/A
1992	3.526152	259524.8	6.056989	42338.35	N/A	N/A
1993	3.225455	237393.5	5.560029	38864.6	N/A	N/A
1994	4.618205	339899.9	4.775761	33382.57	N/A	N/A
1995	5.122074	376984.6	4.440541	31039.38	N/A	N/A
1996	5.371018	395306.9	4.903548	34275.8	N/A	N/A
1997	4.209882	309847.3	5.161084	36075.98	N/A	N/A
1998	3.8117	280541.1	6.147598	42971.71	N/A	N/A
1999	3.8117	280541.1	6.150204	42989.93	N/A	N/A
2000	3.287308	241945.9	4.819956	33691.49	N/A	N/A
2001	3.372632	248225.7	8.688743	60734.31	N/A	N/A
2002	3.277086	241193.5	5.960703	41665.31	N/A	N/A
2003	5.843981	430117	5.847312	40872.71	N/A	N/A
2004	7.501553	552114.3	5.843984	40849.45	N/A	N/A
2005	10.00649	736477.7	6.839232	47806.23	2.021	14126.79
2006	6.385382	469964.1	4.669583	32640.39	1.333	9317.67
2007	3.273578	240935.3	4.10565	28698.49	1.376	9618.24
2008	0.959548	70622.73	5.746234	40166.18	1.806	12623.94
2009	0.93609	68896.22	6.920293	48372.85	1.892	13225.08
2010	1.062656	78211.48	6.202876	43358.1	1.548	10820.52
2011	6.722852	494801.9	5.903103	41262.69	1.505	10519.95
2012	2.252768	165803.7	3.708639	25923.39	1.204	8415.96
2013	2.22513	163769.6	5.23871	36618.58	0.946	6612.54
2014	1.032407	75985.16	3.504154	24494.04	N/A	N/A
2015	0.647006	47619.64	1.61581	11294.51	N/A	N/A
2016	2.143436	157756.9	3.284864	22961.2	N/A	N/A
2017	1.630987	120040.6	1.672915	11693.68	N/A	N/A
2018	0.967965	71242.22	3.447812	24100.21	N/A	N/A

The emissions which result from the consumption of energy in the various sub sectors are shown in Tables 4.3 and 4.4. The emissions trend varies linearly with the

quantity of annual yearly consumption and the type of fuel usage. A decomposition of the emissions trend based on the LMDI method is presented for each of the effective parametric variations for the year 2012. Sub sectoral energy intensity, structure and GDP values are needed for a detailed computation. These values are presented in Table 4.5.

Table 4.7 Sub Sectoral GDP Structure (S) and Energy Intensity (I)

Year	Livestock		Fishing		Forestry		Crop production	
	S	I	S	I	S	I	S	I
1988	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
1989	0.039578	N/A	0.083342	0.045	0.04448	0.293	0.8326	0.08263
1990	0.051565	N/A	0.117238	0.038	0.065512	0.252	0.765685	0.112302
1991	0.044869	N/A	0.133999	0.035	0.065497	0.263	0.755634	0.118837
1992	0.041406	N/A	0.102815	0.036	0.064098	0.239	0.791681	0.100357
1993	0.036395	N/A	0.070051	0.035	0.054801	0.204	0.838753	0.068038
1994	0.036806	N/A	0.070616	0.035	0.048825	0.097	0.843752	0.058609
1995	0.023404	N/A	0.070345	0.034	0.04969	0.097	0.856561	0.053971
1996	0.018506	N/A	0.072237	0.032	0.048912	0.067	0.860345	0.053401
1997	0.01286	N/A	0.060452	0.033	0.046535	0.069	0.880153	0.055226
1998	0.011401	N/A	0.053436	0.035	0.047295	0.338	0.887868	0.048584
1999	0.009983	N/A	0.056192	0.029	0.042474	0.063	0.891351	0.042841
2000	0.004878	N/A	0.035706	0.025	0.039562	0.056	0.919854	0.027234
2001	0.004031	N/A	0.031587	0.026	0.034761	0.034	0.929621	0.021026
2002	0.00009	N/A	0.014057	0.021	0.022099	0.023	0.963751	0.009374
2003	0.0000508	N/A	0.010463	0.023	0.017346	0.019	0.97214	0.004596
2004	0.0000473	N/A	0.009163	0.024	0.01519	0.016	0.9756	0.003438
2005	0.0000512	0.55	0.008983	0.026	0.016007	0.016	0.974959	0.003073
2006	0.0000427	0.34	0.007297	0.016	0.013322	0.001	0.979338	0.002013
2007	0.0000387	0.33	0.006491	0.010	0.012755	0.001	0.980715	0.00152
2008	0.0000379	0.40	0.00642	0.008	0.013911	0.0002	0.979631	0.001965
2009	0.0000372	0.38	0.006296	0.009	0.014241	0.032	0.979426	0.002284
2010	0.0000327	0.28	0.005056	0.008	0.015358	0.004	0.979553	0.001971
2011	0.0000283	0.25	0.00402	0.014	0.013168	0.005	0.982784	0.001509
2012	0.0000184	0.18	0.002608	0.006	0.008628	0.001	0.988746	0.000821
2013	0.0000189	0.14	0.002679	0.007	0.008948	0.0001	0.988354	0.000944
2014	0.0000179	N/A	0.002519	0.004	0.00955	0.003	0.987913	0.00096
2015	0.0000212	N/A	0.002597	0.002	0.010134	0.003	0.987247	0.000763
2016	0.0000212	N/A	0.002597	0.005	0.010134	0.008	0.987248	0.000729
2017	0.0000212	N/A	0.002588	0.003	0.010869	0.005	0.986522	0.000638
2018	0.0000214	N/A	0.002691	0.003	0.011662	0.001	0.985625	0.000826

Emissions based on activity:

Referring equation 3.41 and Tables 4.1, 4.2, 4.5 and 4.6, the activity based emissions are calculated as (for 2012 referenced from 2011):

$$\Delta C_{activity1} = \frac{[17408516.84-18299376.34]}{\ln(17408516.84)-\ln(18299376.34)} * \ln\left(\frac{344913.02}{205936.69}\right) + \frac{(172822.5774-275084.5998)}{\ln(172822.5774)-\ln(275084.5998)} * \ln\left(\frac{344913.02}{205936.69}\right)$$

$$\Delta C_{activity2} = \Delta C_{activity1} + \frac{(221300.856-996590.568)}{\ln(221300.856)-\ln(996590.568)} * \ln\left(\frac{3009.64}{2759.18}\right) + \frac{(165803.7-494801.9)}{\ln(165803.7)-\ln(494801.9)} * \ln\left(\frac{909.92}{842.40}\right)$$

$$\Delta C_{activity3} = \Delta C_{activity2} + \frac{(25923.39-41262.69)}{\ln(25923.39)-\ln(41262.69)} * \ln\left(\frac{909.92}{842.40}\right) + \frac{(8415.96-10519.95)}{\ln(8415.96)-\ln(10519.95)} * \ln\left(\frac{6.41}{5.92}\right)$$

$$\Delta C_{total\ activity} = 9390510.713\ tCO_2$$

Following similar computations for the activity effect, economic structure, intensity, energy matrix and the emissions effects tabulations are made and presented in Table 4.8:

Table 4.8 Summary of Carbon Dioxide Emissions Decoupling

Year	$\Delta C_{activity}$ tCO_2	ΔC_{str} tCO_2	ΔC_{int} tCO_2	ΔC_{mix} tCO_2	ΔC_{emf} tCO_2
1990	-1425239.943	236015.2307	2964418.959	7.293471035	-0.023129335
1991	-263839.4078	-105825.5919	780137.8695	0.262925875	0.015109887
1992	1458941.403	401625.4338	-2304001.295	-96.66863285	0.00994906
1993	4762011.292	122602.3904	-4989402.716	-0.513973806	0.000456137
1994	373632.7452	-153038.1248	-3078956.722	204.0214531	-0.001180779
1995	963782.027	181659.0783	-885714.1104	7.773063018	-0.058959339
1996	975360.9517	41365.10802	-557505.1726	1.899674841	0.024474411
1997	932107.215	156519.3437	452358.2536	-37.00622848	0.008101499
1998	2355322.482	115913.6621	2760469.593	-19.25229413	-0.009679931
1999	2590854.730	127505.028	3036516.552	-21.178	-0.011
2000	5744960.935	180715.6056	-6005027.774	-1.229430544	0.045869085

2001	8001989.593	-51972.11545	-4290550.838	898.8639873	-0.045984053
2002	13005201.98	-179799.2173	-13534561.36	200.1000672	-0.01689289
2003	6616806.813	-252518.6799	-10224844.96	-30.40368519	0.041909866
2004	3311384.14	-173581.8462	-3649885.92	44.45213261	0.00382981
2005	1934319.609	40251.49111	-1237800.448	15.3993118	0.028657987
2006	2879310.075	-162268.9426	-6182124.099	-191.6481335	-0.040910969
2007	1639454.201	-33872.0513	-2905260	-428.6333289	-0.055228821
2008	1030567.225	-9073.119136	2726907.017	-5063.618396	0.025845275
2009	1792285.835	14329.40008	6300857.67	59.2867501	-0.004292706
2010	4420416.601	133213.2877	-6590875.421	98.02074967	-0.002490093
2011	4731172.331	-140919.9836	-4782365.721	16655.30271	0.004525567
2012	9390510.713	-253007.6931	-12095622.98	-1189.36366	-0.036337953
2013	984082.1592	873.2764899	2506500.834	100.167895	0.050344589
2014	3248108.43	-5547.557793	985714.7791	1016.176306	-0.00836994
2015	1699793.792	33410.96737	-5537990.941	-580.9843125	-0.011206826
2016	276305.9834	21.77990336	830713.7889	-47.94674592	0.012375668
2017	1412909.302	142326.3418	-3697377.797	-244.1324782	-0.053317438
2018	1062971.316	58987.77735	4352349.16	-86.664152	0.025252191

The results from emissions decoupling shows the relative contribution of the changes due to the parts of index decomposition. For the years considered, the changes in emissions are predominantly observed in the activity effect. For the years 1991 through 2018, the activity indicator shows a large contribution to accumulation of emissions. Only the years 1989 and 1991 recorded a reduction in the overall emissions from the activity effect. In general, the trend of the emissions over the years for the agricultural sector increases as shown in Fig. 4.3.

Fig 4.3. Carbon dioxide emissions from the agricultural sector

In summary, as reflected on the results shown in Fig. 4.3, crop production accounts for a higher part of emissions, followed by forestry, and then fishing.

4.4 PROBABILISTIC RESULTS

The results from a consideration of the effect of the form of energy consumption on economic growth is shown using the method of multiple regression in Tables 4.9 and 4.10. Due to paucity of data, three sub sectors were considered in the analysis instead of the four earlier compiled.

Table 4.9. Summary of Regression Results

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value
Intercept	-280321	101973.6	-2.74895	0.010727
CROP	0.030808	0.004443	6.934325	2.31E-07
FORESTRY	-0.01779	0.01227	-1.44958	0.159131
FISHING	-0.05506	0.12247	-0.44958	0.656739

Table 4.10. Summary of Regression Statistics

Regression Statistics	
Multiple R	0.889457
R Square	0.791134
Adjusted R Square	0.767034
Standard Error	84898.35
Observations	30

The net gross domestic products from crop production, forestry and fishing is seen to be positively correlated with the different emissions from these subsectors. The results showed that carbon emissions from forestry and fishing have a negative impact on gross domestic product (GDP) in Nigeria. A unit rise in gas fuel emissions from forestry and fishing will lead to 0.01779 and 0.05504 units decline in GDP. However, with respect to crop production, corresponding unit rise will result in an increase in GDP by 0.030808 units as a multiple of the base economic value.

The other performance criteria include the standard error test, the t-statistic, and the coefficient of determination (or R-Squared). The standard error value of emissions

from crop production (0.004443) is less than half the value of its corresponding coefficient (0.22) which suggests that emissions from crop production have a huge impact on economic growth. On the other hand, the standard error term from forestry (0.01227) is just slightly less than the value of its coefficients 0.01779 in absolute terms. This implies that emission from forestry has minimal impact on economic growth in Nigeria represented by GDP. Furthermore, the results also show that the emissions from fishing have negligibly small bearing on the gross domestic product in the agricultural sector. The standard error from the analysis for fishing (0.12247) is slightly higher than its corresponding coefficient in the regression result (0.05506). The results demonstrate the realities involved in the agricultural sector. The standard error value of emissions from crop production (0.004443) is less than half the value of its corresponding coefficient (0.22) which suggests that emissions from crop production have a huge impact on economic growth. On the other hand, the standard error term from forestry (0.01227) is just slightly less than the value of its coefficients 0.01779 in absolute terms. This implies that emission from forestry has minimal impact on economic growth in Nigeria represented by GDP. Furthermore, the results also show that the emissions from fishing have negligibly small bearing on the gross domestic product in the agricultural sector. The standard error from the analysis for fishing (0.12247) is slightly higher than its corresponding coefficient in the regression result (0.05506). The results demonstrate the realities involved in the agricultural sector.

5. CONCLUSION

The study addressed the quantitative relationship between energy consumption, corresponding emissions and economic growth to assist in creating one of several energy management blueprints necessary for a greener environment. The agricultural sector was considered with focus on crop production, forestry, fishing and livestock. Data on energy consumption from different energy carriers and corresponding sectoral gross domestic product was used based on simple decomposition models and regression analysis. The areas covered were presentation of various energy consumption patterns in the agricultural sector, quantification of the emissions stemming from these energy use as well as the associated gross domestic product and development of a methodology for assessing the impact of energy consumption on economic growth and emissions. They highlight the particular effect of the consumption of several energy carriers on both economic growth and environmental degradation. The results will help guide policy makers and investors in making wise energy investment decisions in the near future.

References

- Abiodun R (2003) Fuel price Hike Spells Doom for Nigeria's Forest. Retrieved from <http://www.islamonline.net/English/index.shtml>.
- Adesina, F.A and Adejuwon, J.O., (2008). Climate Change and Potential Impact on Biomass Energy Production in Nigeria. A Preliminary Assessment. Paper Presented At The International Workshop On The Impact Of Global Climate Change On Energy Development, Lagos, Nigeria, March 28-30.
- Afshar K, Bigdeli N. (2011). Data analysis and short term load forecasting in Iran electricity market using singular spectral analysis (SSA). *Energy*; doi:10.1016/j.energy.2011.02.003, in press.
- Al-Ali, M., Dincer, I. (2014). Energetic and Exergetic Studies of a Multigenerational Solar-Geothermal System, *Applied Thermal Engineering* doi: 10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2014.06.033.
- Ang, B. W. and Lee, P. W. (1996). Decomposition of industrial energy consumption: the energy coefficient approach. *Energy Economics* 18(1-2):129-43.
- Ang, B. W. (1995). Multilevel decomposition of industrial energy consumption. *Energy Economics* 17(1):39-51.
- Ang, B.W. (2004). Decomposition Analysis for Policy Making in Energy: which is the Preferred Method? *Energy Policy* 32, 1131-1139.
- Ang, B.W. (2005). The LMDI Approach to Decomposition Analysis: a Practical Guide. *Energy Policy* 33, 867-871.

- Ang, B.W., Liu, F. L., Chew, E. (2003). Perfect decomposition techniques in energy and environmental analysis. *Energy Policy* 31, 1561–1566.
- Ang, B.W., Liu, F. L., Chung, H. S. (2002). Index numbers and the Fisher ideal index approach in energy decomposition analysis. Research Report 38/2002, Department of Industrial and Systems Engineering, National University of Singapore.
- Apergis, N., Payne JE. (2011). The renewable energy consumption-growth nexus in Central America. *Applied Energy* 88(1):343-7.
- Aqeel A, Butt MS (2001). The Relationship between Energy Consumption and Economic Growth in Pakistan. *Asia-Pac. Dev. J.* 8(2): 101-109.
- Asafu-Adjaye J (2000). The relationship between energy consumption, energy prices and economic growth: time series evidence from Asian developing countries. *Energy Econ.* 22. 615-625.
- Badmus, I., and Osunleke, A. S. (2010). Application of energy and exergy analyses for efficient energy utilisation in the Nigerian residential sector. *International Journal of Exergy*, 7(3), 352. doi:10.1504/ijex.2010.031989
- Badmus, I., Osunleke, A., Fagbenle, R., and Oyewola, M. (2012). Energy and exergy analyses of the Nigerian transportation sector from 1980 to 2010. *International Journal of Energy and Environmental Engineering*, 3(1), 23. doi:10.1186/2251-6832-3-23.
- Badmus, I., Osunleke, A., Fagbenle, R., and Oyewola, M. (2014). End Use Energy Utilization Efficiency of Nigerian Residential Sector. *Frontiers in Energy*, 8(3): 322-334

- Baltimore, C and Tudok, R., (2010). Relationships Between Energy And GNP. *Journal of Energy and Development*, Vol 3, pp. 401-403.
- Bhattacharya M, Paramati RS, Ozturk I, Bhattacharya S. (2016). The effect of renewable energy consumption on economic growth: evidence from top 38 countries. *Appl Energy* 162:733-41.
- Bhattacharya, M., Paramati, R. S., Ozturk, I., Bhattacharya, S. (2016). The effect of renewable energy consumption on economic growth: evidence from top 38 countries. *Applied Energy*, 162:733-41.
- Bicer, Y., Dincer, I. (2015). Development of a multigeneration system with underground coal gasification integrated to bitumen extraction applications for oil sands. *Energy Conversion and Management* 106 235–248.
- Birol, F. (2007). World energy prospects and challenges. Melbourne: Blackwell publishing. Chen PF, Lee CC. Is energy consumption per capita broken stationary? New evidence from regional-based panels. *Energy Policy* 2007; 35(6):3526–40.
- Bowden, N., and Payne, J. E. (2009). The causal relationship between U.S. energy consumption and real output: a disaggregated analysis. *J Pol Model* 31(2):180-8.
- Canay, I. A. (2011). A simple approach to quantile regression for panel data. *Economics Journal* 14 (3): 368-86.
- Costantini, V., and Martini, C. (2009). The causality between energy consumption and economic growth: a multi sectoral analysis using non stationary cointegrated panel data. Department of Economics Roma Tre University, working paper 102.

ECN - Energy Commission of Nigeria (2003) National Energy Policy. Federal Republic of Nigeria, Abuja.

ECN - Energy Commission of Nigeria (2005) Renewable Energy Master Plan

Erbaykal, E. (2008) Disaggregate Energy consumption and Economic Growth: Evidence from Turkey. *International research Journal of Finance and Economics* 20, 172-179.

Famuyide OO, Anamayi SE, Usman JM (2011) Energy Resources' Pricing Policy And Its Implications On Forestry And Environmental Policy Implementation In Nigeria. *Continental J Sustainable Development* 2:1-7.

Galindo LM. Short-and long-run demand for energy in Mexico: a cointegration approach. *Energy Policy* 2005; 33(9):1179-85.

Gozgor, G., Lau, C. K. M., and Lu, Z. (2018). Energy consumption and economic growth: New evidence from the OECD countries. *Energy*, 153, 27-34. doi:10.1016/j.energy.2018.03.158.

Hassoun, A., Dincer, I. (2015). Analysis and performance assessment of a multigenerational system powered by Organic Rankine Cycle for a net zero energy house. *Applied Thermal Engineering* 76 25-36.

Hondroyannis G, Lolos S, Papapetrou E. Energy consumption and economic growth: assessing the evidence from Greece. *Energy Economics* 2002; 24(4):319-36.

- Islam, S., Dincer, I., Yilbas, B. S. (2015). Energetic and exergetic performance analyses of a solar energy-based integrated system for multigeneration including thermoelectric generators. *Energy* 93 1246-1258.
- Jumbe, C.B.L. (2004) Congregation and causality between electricity consumption and GDP: empirical evidence from Malawi. *Energy Economics* 26, 61-68.
- Karekezi, R. (1997). Renewable Energy Technologies in Africa, Zed Books Limited with African Energy Policy Research Network (AFREPREN) and Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI).
- Lee, C. C., and Chang, C. P. (2005). Structural breaks, energy consumption, and economic growth revisited: evidence from Taiwan. *Energy Economics* 27 (6): 857–72.
- Lee, C. C. and Chien, M. S. (2010). Dynamic modelling of energy consumption, capital stock, and real income in G-7 countries. *Energy Economics* 32(3):564–81.
- Lise W, Montfort KV. Energy consumption and GDP in Turkey: is there a cointegration relationship? *Energy Economics* 2007; 29:1166–78.
- Mesih, R.A and Mesih,T. (2009). Causality between Income and Emission: A Country Group Specific Econometric Analysis, *Ecological Economics*, 40 351-367.
- Morimoto R, Hope C (2001). The impact of electricity supply on economic growth in Sri Lanka. *Judge Institute of Management Res. Paper*.
- Nigeria National Bureau of Statistics (NNBS). Distribution of household by type of fuel. 2012–10–08, <http://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng>.

- Obadote D J. Energy crisis in Nigeria: technical issues and solutions. Power Sector Prayer Conference. Abuja, Nigeria, 2009: 1–9.
- Okafor, E. C. N., and Joe-Uzuegbu, C. K. A. (2010). Challenges to Development of Renewable Energy for Electric Power Sector in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research* 2(2):211–216.
- Ozlu, S., Dincer, I. (2015). Development and analysis of a solar and wind energy based multigeneration system. *Solar Energy* 122 1279–1295.
- Porter, A. and Brown, H. J. (2009). Energy Consumption, Economic Growth and Prices; A Reassessment using Panel VECM for Developed and Developing Countries, *Energy Policy*. Vol.35, pp. 2481-2490.
- Robalino L., Garcia R., Golpe A., and Mena N. (2013). System dynamics modelling and the Environmental Kuznets Curve in Ecuador (1980-2025). *Energy Policy* 67, 923-931.
- Rufael, W. (2006). Electricity consumption and Economic growth: A time series experience for 17 African countries. *Energy Policy* 34, 1106-1114.
- Sanglimsuwan, K. S. (2011). Carbon Dioxide Emissions and Economic Growth: An Econometric Analysis. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*. ISSN 1450 – 2887, Issue 67.
- Sari R, Soytas, U. (2004). Disaggregate energy consumption, employment and income in Turkey. *Energy Economics* 26(3):335–44.
- Sharifishourabi, M., Ratlamwala, T., Alimoradiyan, H., Sadeghizadeh, E. (2016). Performance Assessment of a Multi-Generation System Based on Organic

Rankine Cycle. *Iranian Journal of Science and Technology, Transactions of Mechanical Engineering* 3 225-232.

Sharma, S. S. (2010). The relationship between energy and economic growth: Empirical evidence from 66 countries. *Applied Energy*, 87(11), 3565–3574. doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2010.06.015.

Soytas, U; and Sari, R. (2003). Energy consumption and GDP: causality relationship in G-7 countries and emerging markets. *Energy Economics* 25, 33-37.

Soytas, U; Sari, R; Ozdemir, O. (2001). Energy consumption and GNP Relation in Turkey. A Cointegration and Vector Error Correction Analysis, *Global Business and Technology Association*. 838-844.

Stern, D. (2009). Economic Growth and Environmental Degradation: the Environmental Kuznets Curve and Sustainable Development, *World Development*, 24, 1151-1160.

Suleman, F., Dincer, I., Agelin-Chaab, M. (2014). Development of an integrated renewable energy system for multigeneration. *Energy* 78 196-204.

Sun, J. W. (2003). Dematerialization in Finnish energy use, 1972-1996, *Energy Economics*, 25: 23-32.

Sun, J. W. (2001). Energy demand in the fifteen European Union countries by 2010 a forecasting model based on the decomposition approach. *Energy*, 26: 549-60.

Tao, Z. (2010). Scenarios of China's oil consumption per capita (OCPC) using a hybrid Factor Decomposition–System Dynamics (SD) simulation. *Energy* 35 168–180.

- Torras, M., and Boyce, J. K. (2008). Income, inequality, and pollution: Reassessment of the Environmental Kuznets Curve. *Ecological Economics*, 147-160.
- Williams, C. E. (1998). Reaching the African Female Farmers with Innovative Extension Approaches: Success and Challenges for the Future. *Paper Presented to the International Workshop on Women Agricultural Intensification and Household Food Security At University of Cape Coast, Ghana, 25-28 June.*
- Zou, G; and Chau, K.W. (2005). Short and long run effects between oil consumption and Economic growth in China. *Energy policy*.